

1 **Geographic variation in genetic and demographic performance:**
2 **new insights from an old biogeographical paradigm**

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18
19 **ABSTRACT**

20 The ‘centre–periphery hypothesis’ (CPH) is a long-standing postulate in ecology that states
21 that genetic variation and demographic performance of a species decrease from the centre to
22 the edge of its geographic range. This hypothesis is based on an assumed concordance
23 between geographical peripherality and ecological marginality such that environmental
24 conditions become harsher towards the limits of a species range. In this way, the CPH sets the
25 stage for understanding the causes of distribution limits. To date, no study has examined
26 conjointly the consistency of these postulates. In an extensive literature review we discuss the
27 birth and development of the CPH and provide an assessment of the CPH by reviewing 248
28 empirical studies in the context of three main themes. First, a decrease in species occurrence
29 towards their range limits was observed in 81% of studies, while only 51% demonstrated

30 reduced abundance of individuals. A decline in genetic variation, increased differentiation
31 among populations and higher rates of inbreeding were demonstrated by roughly one in two
32 studies (47, 45 and 48%, respectively). However, demographic rates, size and population
33 performance less often followed CPH expectations (20–30% of studies). We highlight the
34 impact of important methodological, taxonomic, and biogeographical biases on such
35 validation rates. Second, we found that geographic and ecological marginality gradients are
36 not systematically concordant, which casts doubt on the reliability of a main assumption of
37 the CPH. Finally, we attempt to disentangle the relative contribution of geographical,
38 ecological and historical processes on the spatial distribution of genetic and demographic
39 parameters. While ecological marginality gradients explain variation in species' demographic
40 performance better than geographic gradients, contemporary and historical factors may
41 contribute interactively to spatial patterns of genetic variation. We thereby propose a
42 framework that integrates species' ecological niche characteristics together with current and
43 past range structure to investigate spatial patterns of genetic and demographic variation across
44 species ranges.

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81 I. INTRODUCTION

82 Biogeography is a science that seeks to understand spatial and temporal patterns in the
83 distribution of traits, species, communities and ecosystems (Brown & Lomolino, 1998). It
84 aspires to identify where species occur, how they perform at distinct locations and the spatial,
85 ecological, and historical factors that explain variation in occurrence and performance. The
86 discipline of biogeography thus provides a basis for the investigation of the processes that
87 generate, maintain, and threaten biodiversity (Gaston, 2000, 2003).

88 The ‘centre–periphery’ hypothesis (hereafter CPH) is a major biogeographical paradigm that
89 aims to explain variation in demographic, genetic and ecological characteristics of species
90 across their distribution ranges, and ultimately, the causes of their range limits (Gaston, 2009;
91 Sexton *et al.*, 2009). Based on the assumption that the range of a species is a geographical
92 representation of its ecological niche (*sensu* Hutchinson, 1957), the CPH includes the idea
93 that environmental conditions are optimal near the centre of the range and harsher at the
94 periphery (Brown, 1984). It also holds as a major tenet that populations are more isolated and
95 less abundant near the range limits of a species (Hengeveld & Haeck, 1982; Brown, 1984).
96 Ecological marginality, lower demographic performance and higher isolation are in turn
97 predicted to cause a decrease in genetic diversity within populations (Soulé, 1973; Lawton,

98 1993) and contribute to an increase in genetic differentiation among populations (Da Cunha,
99 Burla & Dobzhansky, 1950; Mayr, 1963; Eckert, Samis & Lougheed, 2008).

100 Many biogeographic studies have produced results that adhere to the predictions of the CPH,
101 which has, as a result, become a sort of ‘accepted principle’ (Hengeveld & Haeck, 1982; Guo
102 *et al.*, 2005; Eckert *et al.*, 2008; de Oliveira *et al.*, 2009) and has frequently been used to
103 develop ecological and evolutionary hypotheses (Holt & Keitt, 2005; Sagarin, Gaines &
104 Gaylord, 2006). Conservation scientists have also used the ideas of the CPH to assess the
105 pertinence of conservation priorities (Lesica & Allendorf, 1995; Gibson, Van Der Marel &
106 Starzomski, 2009; Thompson, Gaudeul & Debussche, 2010; Rehm *et al.*, 2015). In the last 15
107 years, there has been a series of attempts to assess the validity of the CPH for genetic and
108 demographic features (Sagarin & Gaines, 2002*b*; Eckert *et al.*, 2008; Sexton *et al.*, 2009;
109 Abeli *et al.*, 2014). Although genetic diversity and differentiation appear frequently to follow
110 predictions of the CPH (Eckert *et al.*, 2008), abundance and other demographic vital rates
111 (e.g. survival, fecundity) do not generally follow the expected pattern (Channell & Lomolino,
112 2000; Sagarin & Gaines, 2002*b*; Sexton *et al.*, 2009; Abeli *et al.*, 2014). However, whether
113 there actually is a deterioration in environmental conditions towards the periphery of species
114 ranges is frequently overlooked. This is despite the fact that the CPH does not stand if
115 geographically peripheral populations are not ecologically marginal (Soulé, 1973; Chardon *et al.*,
116 2014). Finally, given that environmental conditions and species ranges change over time,
117 populations currently considered to be ecologically or geographically central may have been
118 marginal in the past, and *vice versa*. For this reason, historical centre–periphery gradients,
119 considering stable refuge areas (rear edge) as the ‘centre’ and recently colonized areas
120 (leading edge) as the ‘periphery’, may provide a more accurate context in which to analyse
121 patterns of genetic variation (Cain, 1944; Hampe & Petit, 2005; Carnaval *et al.*, 2009) and/or
122 demographic performance (Adams, 1902; Hampe & Petit, 2005).

123 The concepts of geographic centrality, ecological marginality, and centre of origin have all
124 been used in the CPH literature (Brown, 1984; Hampe & Petit, 2005; Kawecki, 2008), but the
125 interactions between geographical, ecological, and historical gradients have rarely been
126 studied. At the same time, lumping different gradients into the general category of centre–
127 periphery gradients might lead to misconceptions of the factors affecting the distribution of
128 genetic variation and demographic performance (Pironon *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, the CPH
129 assumes that genetic and demographic features are interdependent, and thus that they show
130 the same centre–periphery pattern of variation (Carson, 1959; Brussard, 1984; Eckert *et al.*,
131 2008). However, this assumption is contradicted by the fact that there is wide-ranging support
132 for the CPH in terms of patterns of genetic variation (Eckert *et al.*, 2008) but little support in
133 terms of spatial patterns of demographic rates (Sagarin & Gaines, 2002*b*; Sexton *et al.*, 2009;
134 Abeli *et al.*, 2014). Merging species’ information for the different components of the CPH
135 would help clarify such inconsistency. Finally, it has been proposed that the CPH might only
136 be pertinent for some particular organisms, or in a subset of biogeographical regions, or at
137 certain spatial scales, but very few studies have attempted to address this issue (Sagarin *et al.*,
138 2006; Eckert *et al.*, 2008).

139 Herein, we first trace the long and complex history of the CPH from pioneer theoretical and
140 empirical studies to contemporary analyses. Second, we test whether empirical studies support
141 the predictions of the CPH by updating results of previous reviews of a particular aspect of
142 the CPH, and by linking the aspects of the CPH in a single overall analysis. This analysis
143 aims to tackle a range of taxonomic, biogeographic, and methodological issues raised in
144 previous reviews. In addition, our study differs from previous reviews in that we first evaluate
145 whether the basic assumption of the hypothesis is always checked and verified (i.e. that
146 environmental conditions become marginal towards the periphery), and secondly attempt to
147 disentangle the relative effects of geographical, ecological and historical centre–periphery

148 gradients on the distribution of genetic variation and demographic performance. This provides
149 for a critical assessment of the CPH that allows us to represent and understand more clearly
150 geographic patterns and the causes of species range limits, as well as the relative conservation
151 value and vulnerability of central and peripheral populations.

152

153 **II. HISTORY OF THE ‘CENTRE–PERIPHERY’ HYPOTHESIS (CPH)**

154 **(1) The pioneers (1900–1950)**

155 Analysis of variation in species’ properties across geographical range has a long history. From
156 the early days of such work, there has been a marked dichotomy between two lines of inquiry,
157 one concerning the general performance of populations or individuals, and the other
158 concerning genetic variation.

159 The idea that species become rarer and perform less well at their range margins due to less-
160 optimal environmental conditions goes back to the 19th century. Darwin (1859, pp. 69–78)
161 discussed “the rigour of the climate [...] on the confines of the geographical range” of taxa,
162 and noted that “some species [were] gradually getting rarer and rarer, and finally
163 disappearing” along geographical gradients. The study of geographic distribution limits was
164 also developing at that time (Wallace, 1876). Specific interest in geographic variation in
165 species’ demographic performance across regions arose in the early 20th century. Based on
166 the available observations of the fauna of the USA and knowledge of historical refugia at that
167 time, Adams (1902) first proposed that species’ abundance would be highest in their historical
168 centres of origin. Simultaneously, other empirical (Cowles, 1901; Transeau, 1903, 1905) and
169 theoretical (Shelford, 1911) studies suggested that the centres of abundance of plant and
170 animal species could be defined by optimal ecological conditions, mainly climate. For
171 example, based on botanical observations in the eastern USA, Cowles (1901, p. 83) claimed
172 that “each species varies in habitat in different regions, and [...] in general a species can grow

173 in the largest number of plant societies at its center of distribution, since there the climatic
174 conditions favor it most highly”. Similarly, Transeau (1905, p. 877) stated that North
175 American trees were most abundant in the centres of distributions, where “the complex of
176 climatic factors most favorable to the development of this type of vegetation is [...] localized
177 and that as we depart from such centers we find conditions more and more unfavorable”.

178 Additionally, it was acknowledged that species had great difficulties in establishing beyond
179 their required environmental conditions, with only occasional observation of vagrant
180 individuals beyond the species distribution area (‘accidental’ *sensu* Grinnell, 1922). Beyond
181 abundance, some studies also found a lower individual performance in marginal populations
182 of both animal and plant taxa, especially in terms of reproductive output (Salisbury, 1926;
183 Filipjev, 1929). However, not surprisingly, these pioneer observations had difficulties that
184 hampered the production of meaningful conclusions, such as a frequent focus on vegetation
185 units or communities rather than single species (but see Gleason, 1926) and scarce or, at best
186 incomplete, data across the range of a given species (Griggs, 1914; Salisbury, 1926).

187 The interest in variation of species’ genetic characteristics across their ranges also arose early
188 in the 20th century, albeit slightly later and rather independently of demographic studies. The
189 investigation of genetic patterns was first framed in a historical context of species’ migrations
190 and dispersal rather than in a static geographical perspective. Before intraspecific studies
191 emerged, Adams (1902) had predicted higher species richness in the historical centres of
192 origin of taxonomic clades. Later, several authors noted differences across species ranges in
193 the abundance of varieties and genetic polymorphism. Vavilov (1926, p. 175) observed in
194 many cultivated plants that “the basic centers of origin [...] appear, as a rule, to be found
195 where a striking diversity of types is accumulated”, and Turrill (1939, p. 230) also noted for a
196 few wild taxa that “towards the margins of their migrations species are less polymorphic”.

197 Notably, both authors acknowledged the existence of exceptions due to complicating factors
198 such as geographical barriers.
199 Some theoretical approaches to these patterns proposed that species would suffer random
200 losses in allelic diversity in the course of colonization events or range expansion (Reinig,
201 1938). At this time, the historical centres of species origin, associated with increased
202 polymorphism, were explicitly differentiated from the centres of highest abundance (and
203 highest individual size), which were in turn related to climatic favourability (Cain, 1944).
204 There were also early mentions of the existence of ‘marked variational forms’ (i.e. greater
205 genetic differentiation) in the geographic periphery of species’ distributions, especially at the
206 rear edge due to environmental stress (Good, 1931). Of course these pioneering studies of
207 phenotypic variation were limited by small sample sizes and a lack of genetic tools at that
208 time.

209

210 **(2) Towards the formulation of hypotheses (1950–1990)**

211 *(a) Demography*

212 Ordination studies of vegetation in the 1950s and 1960s provided the first detailed data on
213 intraspecific variation in abundance (Curtis & McIntosh, 1951; Whittaker, 1956, 1960; Monk,
214 1965). In contrast with previous naturalist observations, these studies relied on quantitative
215 analyses. With exceptions, they revealed that bell-shaped curves of abundance were very
216 common along environmental gradients (Austin, 1976). However, studies were frequently
217 focused on the relative abundance of individuals of each species within the communities, and
218 analysed environmental or geographical gradients of local extent rather than across whole
219 distribution ranges.

220 In the early 1980s, data on species’ distribution and abundance were increasingly available in
221 the form of atlases, floras and more conventional studies, which allowed the first general

222 assessments of the CPH in different taxonomic groups. Two influential reviews (Hengeveld &
223 Haeck, 1982; Brown, 1984) proposed that patterns of higher abundance of individuals in
224 range centres could be a general phenomenon. Haeck & Hengeveld (1981) attributed this
225 pattern to a gradient in suitability of a few key environmental parameters, which reach a
226 physiological optimum in the range centre ('optimum-response surface'). Brown (1984)
227 proposed a more mathematical explanation in which the effects of multiple, independently
228 varying environmental factors depict the distribution of species requirements for survival and
229 reproduction with a bell-shaped curve. Although these authors acknowledged the underlying
230 influence of the environment, they clearly emphasized the existence of a geographical pattern,
231 unlike previous studies. Since then, much empirical research has been carried out on animal
232 and plant species to test what has become known as the 'abundant-centre hypothesis' (Carter
233 & Prince, 1985; Caughley *et al.*, 1988; Carey, Watkinson & Gerard, 1995; Curnutt, Pimm &
234 Maurer, 1996; Blackburn *et al.*, 1999b).

235 In addition to changes in abundance, many authors began reporting, mostly on insect taxa,
236 higher extinction risk and demographic variability in populations at range edges due to poor
237 or fluctuating environmental conditions (Birch, 1957; Nicholson, 1958; Richards, 1961;
238 Whittaker, 1971; but see Grant & Antonovics, 1978). This could be explained theoretically by
239 a higher susceptibility of peripheral populations to density-independent factors (Gaston,
240 1990), because slight variation in abiotic conditions could hinder species persistence or
241 reproduction. However, higher demographic variability was also predicted for central
242 populations assuming higher abundances in the centre and a positive relationship between
243 population numbers and variability in these numbers (May, 1981). Despite a growing
244 consensus for central populations to have higher abundance and population growth rates
245 (Mayr, 1963; Soulé, 1973), not all vital rates were predicted to decline towards range margins,
246 even when abundance is greatest at the centre (Maurer & Brown, 1989). Overall, the expected

247 CPH pattern was demonstrated for some but not all demographic properties even within a
248 given species.

249

250 *(b) Genetic variation*

251 Advances in genetics stimulated the analysis of patterns in genetic variation across species
252 ranges in the 1950s, especially on *Drosophila* species. Interestingly, although geographic
253 peripherality and ecological marginality were commonly associated, at that time authors
254 emphasized the ecological status of populations rather than their geographical location to
255 explain genetic patterns. A general pattern of a reduced chromosomal polymorphism in
256 marginal populations emerged from the first empirical studies (Da Cunha *et al.*, 1950;
257 Townsend, 1952; Carson, 1955; Goldschmidt, 1956; Stalker, 1964; Bantock & Price, 1975).
258 Da Cunha *et al.* (1950) highlighted the role of habitat diversity in promoting genetic variation
259 in the range centre, whereas Carson (1955, 1959) argued that selection in more fluctuating
260 peripheral populations would favour chromosomal monomorphism, which allows higher
261 flexibility for gene recombination. This is because polymorphism, commonly due to
262 inversions, results in locked combinations of genes that limit recombination (Carson, 1955).
263 For allelic diversity, most early studies on animals also suggested higher polymorphism in
264 central populations (reviewed in Mayr, 1963; Soulé, 1973). These authors discussed the
265 relative influence of stochastic processes, induced by spatial isolation, reduced gene flow, and
266 strong selection, in marginal locations. However, some animals, such as *Drosophila* species,
267 showed no reduction in allelic diversity in marginal populations (Soulé, 1973), a result that
268 was attributed to a homogenizing effect of high connectivity among populations of vagile
269 taxa. In addition, some authors highlighted the potential differences in centre–periphery
270 patterns between the commonly measured neutral markers, more affected by stochastic
271 processes, and traits that better reflect the action of natural selection (Brussard, 1984). Finally,

272 besides trends in within-population genetic diversity, evolutionary biologists began to exhibit
273 more interest in the possibility of greater genetic differentiation among peripheral
274 populations, i.e. in more isolated areas with less gene flow (Mayr *et al.*, 1954; Brown, 1957;
275 Mayr, 1963).

276 Thus, unlike the pioneering studies, later papers began to stress contemporary rather than
277 historical factors as drivers of genetic variation in different parts of a species range. In
278 addition, the second half of the 20th century witnessed initial attempts to link genetic and
279 demographic patterns by predicting that variation in abundance across ranges would
280 determine differences in inbreeding coefficients, isolation by distance, and the relative role of
281 density-independent *versus* density-dependent factors on selection (e.g. Haldane, 1956;
282 Carson, 1959; Mayr, 1963). However, the generality of such postulates was limited; detailed
283 information on both demographic and genetic patterns was only collected for *Drosophila*
284 species, in which range-wide genetic variation could be explained by the potential roles of
285 differences in selective regimes, abundance patterns and historical events (Brussard, 1984).
286 Many studies have been carried out across the distribution ranges of different animals and
287 plants since the 1970s, most showing higher genetic diversity in the centre of the distribution
288 (Dessauer & Nevo, 1969; Yeh & Layton, 1979), although some studies showed no pattern or
289 indeed the opposite pattern to that predicted by the CPH (e.g. Prakash, 1973; Tigerstedt,
290 1973). In addition, an interest emerged in analysing the genetic consequences of poleward
291 migrations since the last glaciation, with most empirical work illustrating a decline in genetic
292 variation in northern range-limit populations in the northern hemisphere (e.g. Dessauer &
293 Nevo, 1969; Highton & Webster, 1976; Schwaegerle & Schaal, 1979).

294

295 **(3) Evaluation and refinement of hypotheses (into the 21st century)**

296 *(a) Syntheses of empirical patterns*

297 From the 1990s onwards, an ever-increasing number of CPH tests have been conducted on a
298 wide array of organisms, on different continents, at different spatial scales, and using a high
299 diversity of methodological approaches to investigate various genetic and demographic traits
300 (Fig. 1; see online Supporting Information, Appendix S1). A large number of studies have
301 examined patterns of demographic performance across species ranges. Contrary to
302 expectations, several initial reviews found no general support for the CPH for demographic
303 traits such as abundance, individual vital rates or population growth rates (Sagarin & Gaines,
304 2002b; Sexton *et al.*, 2009; Abeli *et al.*, 2014), although a tendency for higher demographic
305 variability in peripheral situations was detected (Sexton *et al.*, 2009). Several recent studies
306 have also challenged the view that species' geographical range limits match their
307 environmental tolerance limits (Chardon *et al.*, 2014; Hargreaves, Samis & Eckert, 2014). The
308 idea that centre–periphery gradients associated with either geographic peripherality or
309 ecological marginality should be distinguished was thus emerging.

310 More recently, some authors have looked more closely at the assumptions of the CPH by
311 taking a less static view of the CPH in which the distribution of species' demographic
312 performance reflects temporal range changes, primarily from post-glacial recolonization
313 events to contemporary extinction/colonization dynamics after environmental change (Hampe
314 & Petit, 2005). For instance, species have been found to be more resilient to range
315 contractions in the periphery of their distribution than in the centre, due to lower
316 anthropogenic effects (Channell & Lomolino, 2000). However, very few studies have
317 compared demographic rates of rear- and leading-edge populations (Hampe & Petit, 2005; but
318 see Purves, 2009; Pironon *et al.*, 2015).

319 The most comprehensive empirical reviews of the CPH in relation to patterns of genetic
320 variation in plants and animals have shown a general trend for lower genetic diversity within
321 populations and higher differentiation among populations in the periphery (Eckert *et al.*,

2008; see also Johannesson & Andre, 2006). However, these patterns are far from being universal, and several authors have pointed out strong taxonomical, biogeographical and sampling-related biases in the available studies. Also, strong selection pressure in marginal areas due to stressful and fluctuating conditions could lead to the appearance of novel adaptations and confer greater evolutionary potential, and thus conservation interest, especially in the context of global warming (Safriel, Volis & Karr, 1994; Lesica & Allendorf, 1995). Moreover, as for demographic patterns, recent studies call for independent analyses of the roles of geography and ecology in shaping range-wide patterns of genetic variation (Lira-Noriega & Manthey, 2014; Sexton, Hangartner & Hoffmann, 2014).

Historical effects on genetic variation have also received much recent attention, with numerous studies focusing on peripheral populations that represent recent colonization events. In general, such leading-edge populations show lower genetic variation than central populations (Hewitt, 1996, 2000). On the other hand, some authors have pinpointed the relevance of frequently overlooked rear-edge populations, which might show unique genetic properties due to their persistence in stressful or exceptional conditions, or due to their older history (Hewitt, 1996; Hampe & Petit, 2005). Guo (2012) emphasized the importance of evaluating central–peripheral and latitudinal gradients together, considering both historical and contemporary events, to understand biological patterns across ranges, as highlighted several decades ago by Cain (1944).

341

342 *(b) From patterns to processes: linking the CPH to theory on range limits*

343 The CPH postulates that environmental gradients generate spatial variation in population performance, and range limits reflect the inability of individuals to establish beyond their range limits due to physiological constraints imposed by suboptimal environments (Caughley *et al.*, 1988; Gaston, 2009). Additionally, the lower level of genetic variability within

347 populations that is predicted to occur close to distribution limits may impede population-level
348 adaptation to different ecological conditions (Blows & Hoffmann, 2005; Takahashi *et al.*,
349 2016), and thus limit colonization beyond range boundaries. In parallel with the empirical
350 work described above, theoretical work has examined the origin and maintenance of stable
351 range limits (reviewed by Sexton *et al.*, 2009), and some of these models have been based on
352 the predictions of the CPH, making explicit assumptions of a decrease in population density
353 towards range edges (e.g. García-Ramos & Kirkpatrick, 1997; Alleaume-Benharira, Pen &
354 Ronce, 2006). These models open new perspectives on mechanisms that shape range-wide
355 variation of population genetic and demographic features, and provide a conceptual basis for
356 the analysis of the results of empirical tests of the CPH.

357 Several models have explored how demography (and in particular metapopulation dynamics)
358 can create stable distribution limits (Holt & Keitt, 2000; Holt, 2003; Case *et al.*, 2005).

359 Despite constant habitat quality across the range, the model developed by Holt & Keitt (2000)
360 predicts that habitat availability and local extinction–colonization dynamics can create stable
361 range limits. Additionally, Keitt, Lewis & Holt (2001) have pinpointed the importance of
362 Allee effects to constrain population settlement beyond species range limits, because low
363 density could result in reproductive failure, or a breakdown in biotic interactions (e.g.
364 predation, cooperation).

365 This theoretical framework predicts a decrease in occurrence, abundance and demographic
366 performance towards the periphery, which is in line with predictions of the CPH, despite the
367 fact that no variation in habitat quality is considered. Furthermore, other models have shown
368 how between-species interactions such as competition (Case *et al.*, 2005), predation and
369 parasitism (Hochberg & Ives, 2006) or hybridization (Bridle & Vines, 2007) may play a key
370 role in shaping stable range limits. This research can help understand the relative importance
371 of biotic and abiotic factors in creating distribution limits, as they may act differently across

372 the range (namely the ‘species interactions–abiotic stress hypothesis’ reviewed in Louthan,
373 Doak & Angert, 2015). Finally, merging environmental suitability, biotic interactions and
374 metapopulation dynamics might help provide better insights into source–sink patterns across
375 species’ ranges (Pulliam, 1988, 2000). In this context, some authors have highlighted the
376 importance of characterizing spatial patterns of both habitat suitability and availability to
377 understand demographic differences between central and peripheral populations and the
378 formation of range edges (Keitt *et al.*, 2001; Sexton *et al.*, 2009).

379 The CPH postulates that peripheral populations are smaller, less abundant and more
380 fragmented due to harsher ecological conditions, which as a result may affect levels of both
381 neutral (Ellstrand & Elam, 1993) and adaptive (Bridle, Gavaz & Kennington, 2009) genetic
382 diversity when compared to central populations (Takahashi *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, the
383 low number of individuals may limit the rate of mutational input required to produce migrants
384 adapted to different habitats (Alleaume-Benharira *et al.*, 2006), which may further impede
385 adaptation and thus constrain range expansion. This perspective contrasts with evolutionary
386 models (Bridle & Vines, 2007) that provide alternative hypotheses to explain why species
387 regularly fail to adapt beyond their actual range limits (Lenormand, 2002). Range limits could
388 arise along environmental gradients due to an asymmetrical gene flow from maladapted
389 individuals that migrate from the centre of the range towards peripheries (García-Ramos &
390 Kirkpatrick, 1997; Kirkpatrick & Barton, 1997). Hence, they hinder local adaptation to the
391 range edge and turn peripheral populations into demographic sinks as migrants import
392 phenotypes that diminish population mean fitness (Bridle & Vines, 2007). This effect can be
393 accentuated under the pressure of a predator that impacts peripheral populations, effectively
394 increasing asymmetry in gene flow (Case & Taper, 2000). Predictions arising from this
395 theoretical framework differ from the CPH, because peripheral populations are assumed to
396 exhibit no decrease in genetic diversity, and little differentiation compared to central

397 populations. However, these models predict edge populations to exhibit poor population
398 performance, which fits CPH expectations. On the other hand, gene flow might also bring
399 additional genetic variation that could promote local adaptation in genetically depauperate
400 populations at range limits, and act as a rescue effect (Gomulkiewicz, Holt & Barfield, 1999;
401 Alleaume-Benharira *et al.*, 2006). These mechanisms remain poorly understood (Antonovics,
402 1976; Bridle & Vines, 2007; Gaston, 2009), especially regarding the spatial scales at which
403 gene flow can swamp local adaptation (Sexton & Dickman, 2016). In fact, gene flow can be
404 spatially heterogeneous if there are natural barriers to dispersal (Goldberg & Lande, 2007),
405 and preferential dispersal towards specific habitats might mitigate its disruptive effect, so
406 migrants are not necessarily maladapted to newly colonized sites (Case & Taper, 2000). So
407 far, no evidence of maladaptive gene flow has been identified in plants (Sexton & Dickman,
408 2016), and only a few examples exist for animals (but see Fedorka *et al.*, 2012).

409 A gap has thus appeared during the past 20 years between two parallel research
410 streams with little exchange (Gaston, 2009), i.e. between empirical research on the CPH, and
411 theoretical modelling, which remains largely untested empirically (Sexton *et al.*, 2009). Both
412 demographic and evolutionary theoretical models stress dispersal as a key process in the
413 occurrence of range limits and shaping the distribution of population performance (Bridle &
414 Vines, 2007; Dytham, 2009; Sun & Cheptou, 2012), which is rarely considered in studies of
415 the CPH.

416

417 **III. GLOBAL SURVEY AND ANALYSIS**

418 **(1) Paper selection**

419 To compile a representative data set of articles that have empirically tested the CPH, we
420 selected publications according to a standardized sampling method. First, we extracted all
421 studies cited in the main text and supplementary information of four comprehensive literature

422 reviews of the CPH: Sagarin & Gaines (2002b) for abundant-centre patterns; Sexton *et al.*
423 (2009) for demographic vital rates; Abeli *et al.* (2014) for plant population performance and
424 abundance; and Eckert *et al.* (2008) for genetic diversity and differentiation. We then used the
425 ISI *Web of Knowledge* database to select all papers that have cited at least one of these
426 reviews. Finally, we made a search on the ISI *Web of Knowledge* browser using as key words
427 the centre (“cent*” or “core”) with periphery (“marg*” or “peripher*” or “edge” or “limit*”
428 or “satellite”) and link word “AND”. We restricted our research to the first 250 articles in the
429 field “ecology”. This search was performed on June 30, 2014; papers published after this date
430 are not included in our study. We obtained a total list of 1260 papers that we filtered to retain
431 original articles that explicitly compared central and peripheral populations based on
432 empirical data and in which we could extract species-level results supported by statistical
433 tests. This resulted in a final pool of 248 papers (Fig. 1A, Appendix S1), 127 of which had
434 been included in one or more of the four previous reviews, and 121 of which are novel to our
435 review (Appendix S2).

436

437 **(2) Data collection**

438 Results of the 248 studies were sorted into several broad categories (abundance, population
439 performance, size, genetic variation, and environment). Within each category, studies were
440 classified according to different traits (e.g. genetic diversity, differentiation or inbreeding for
441 the category ‘genetic variation’). Finally, each trait was measured using different indices (e.g.
442 allelic richness and heterozygosity for ‘genetic diversity’).

443 ‘Abundance’ patterns were studied at two scales: *population occupancy* at a regional scale
444 (i.e. number or frequency of populations in a given area) and *abundance of individuals* within
445 a population at a local scale (i.e. population size or density of individuals). ‘Population
446 performance’ was assessed in relation to several vital rates of the populations: *survival*,

447 *growth, fecundity, recruitment*, and the overall *population growth rate*. ‘Size’ covered
448 morphometric measures of individuals. Size was often considered a proxy for growth; hence,
449 we later interpreted our results for size and performance together. We also extracted results
450 concerning the spatial or temporal variability of traits in the ‘Abundance’, ‘Population
451 performance’, and ‘Size’ categories. *Population occupancy* was the only feature for which we
452 found no study on variability. The ‘Genetic variation’ category included measures of three
453 traits: *within-population diversity*, *among-population differentiation*, and *inbreeding*.
454 Finally, in addition to these categories, we regrouped all articles that focused on species
455 environmental conditions. Two features were considered: the mean *environment* which
456 captured differences in mean conditions between central and peripheral populations, and
457 *environmental variability*, which identified differences in environmental conditions among
458 populations within central and peripheral areas (i.e. spatial variability), or within each region
459 over time (i.e. temporal variability). Results for this category are presented separately in
460 Section V.1.

461 For each article, we extracted results at a species level and assessed whether a given trait was
462 significantly higher in central (C) or peripheral (P) populations or not significantly different
463 between the two geographic groups of populations (N). A wide variety of indices have been
464 used, so when several of them were used for a single trait (e.g. genetic diversity estimated by
465 the number of alleles per locus and heterozygosity), we discarded non-significant tests, and
466 assigned one value of C or P per trait only if indices associated with significant statistical tests
467 were all higher in central or peripheral populations. If no difference was statistically
468 significant or if significant trends were detected in opposite directions (e.g. C and P), we
469 considered the result as being null (N). Thus, the total number of tests of the CPH represents
470 the number of comparisons for all species in the 248 articles.

471 The CPH has been tested on a large array of organisms, with a wide variety of sampling
472 protocols. Therefore, we also extracted methodological information from the studied
473 publications. We first aimed to quantify spatial aspects of sampling schemes to assess whether
474 they affect the degree of support for the CPH. We examined three main sampling
475 characteristics (Fig. 2). The first was the relative position of peripheral populations within the
476 species range or ‘degree of isolation’ between peripheral populations and the central part of
477 the distribution. Here, tests were allocated to one of three classes: intermediate (peripheral
478 populations located between the centre and the edge of the range), absolute (peripheral
479 populations at the edge of the range) and beyond (peripheral populations isolated beyond the
480 edge of a continuous range). A second sampling effect involves the ‘spatial extent’ of the
481 study area (i.e. the largest distance between two studied populations). Again, we allocated
482 studies to one of three classes: small-scale studies (< 200 km between the two most distant
483 populations), regional-scale studies (200–2000 km) and continental-scale studies (> 2000
484 km). These classes were adapted from Pearson & Dawson (2003). The third sampling
485 characteristic is ‘range cover’ which assesses the proportion of a species distribution that has
486 been sampled in the study using four percentage classes (0–10%; 10–25%; 25–50%; 50–
487 100%). When not provided directly by the authors in the main text, the extent of species’
488 distributions was extracted from external sources (supplementary information, atlases and
489 internet). Finally, study species were classified by kingdom (plant or animal), and by the
490 biogeographical regions they inhabit (following USDA <http://www.nrcs.usda.gov>).

491

492 **(3) Statistical analyses**

493 Our analysis is based on frequency comparisons using Chi-squared tests of homogeneity. We
494 also conducted binomial tests on the numbers of tests that provide support for the CPH for
495 each trait or feature. First, we tested whether more than 50% of tests provide support for the

496 CPH (hypothesized probability of success of 0.5; i.e. $C > P+N$ for comparisons of mean trait
497 values, $P > C+N$ for comparisons of genetic differentiation and trait variability). If this
498 deviation was not significant, we investigated whether more than one-third of the tests
499 provide support for the CPH (hypothesized probability of success of 0.33; i.e. $C > P$ or $C > N$ for
500 comparisons of mean traits, and $P > C$ or $P > N$ for comparisons of genetic differentiation and
501 trait variability).

502 We used a principal component analysis (PCA) to investigate correlations among the three
503 main sampling characteristics and limit potential redundancy. Given that these variables are
504 semi-quantitative, we recoded them on an ordinal scale before performing the analysis.

505 ‘Spatial extent’ and ‘range cover’ were highly correlated and well summarized by the first
506 axis of the PCA (54% of variability explained; later named ‘scale’) while the second axis was
507 driven by the ‘degree of isolation’ (32% of variation explained; later named ‘isolation’). We
508 therefore used coordinates of each study on these axes as synthetic variables. Then, we fitted a
509 generalized linear model (GLM) for binomial data with support for the hypothesis (yes or no)
510 as a response variable and ‘scale’ and ‘isolation’ as explanatory variables.

511 All analyses were performed using the R software (R development Core Team, 2010) with the
512 *ade4* package for multivariate analysis (Dray & Dufour, 2007) (see Appendix S3 for R script).

513

514 **IV. THE CENTRE–PERIPHERY HYPOTHESIS: THE EVIDENCE**

515 **(1) Multiple approaches**

516 Our database contained 248 papers published between 1968 and 2014 in 89 different journals
517 (Fig. 1A, Appendix S1). Genetic variation was the most studied category with 135 papers
518 representing 301 tests (Fig. 1B). Abundance and population performance were examined in
519 76 papers (176 tests), and 82 papers (262 tests) respectively. Differences in size and
520 ecological conditions were the least-often investigated in 54 papers (95 tests) and 42 papers

521 (96 tests), respectively. No study conjointly analysed genetic variation, population
522 performance and abundance patterns. Most of these empirical studies were conducted in
523 North America and Europe (83% of the articles, Fig. 1C). This over-representation of
524 temperate areas may strongly impact results and limit any global interpretation of trends,
525 which highlights the necessity of analysing its potential bias.

526 Most papers studying the CPH considered a geographical centre–periphery gradient.
527 However, other non-geographical interpretations of central–peripheral gradients were used
528 (Fig. 1D) including ecological gradients with peripheral populations in different (or marginal)
529 conditions (e.g. Hargrove & Rotenberry, 2011; Pouget *et al.*, 2013), and temporal gradients
530 with peripheral areas containing younger (more recently founded) populations (e.g. Tollefsrud
531 *et al.*, 2009; Gassert *et al.*, 2013). This approach was used explicitly when precise data on past
532 distribution were available, for example in relation to post-glacial (Cwynar & MacDonald,
533 1987; Hoban *et al.*, 2010; Jadwiszczak *et al.*, 2011), or recent (Mandak, 2005) colonization.

534 Finally, some authors described a centre–periphery pattern based on the size and/or the
535 density of the population (e.g. Van Rossum & Prentice, 2004; Lemke & Porembski, 2013).

536 Despite the common framework shared by the studies we review here, how the hypothesis is
537 named is rather variable. For the 248 papers that we selected, 168 (67%) did not explicitly
538 name the hypothesis, although their aim was in fact to test some of its predictions. In the
539 remaining 33%, three names were most commonly used: the abundant-centre (47%), the
540 central–marginal (24%), and the centre–periphery (15%) hypotheses. In addition, several
541 authors used various other terms to name the hypothesis (e.g. core-periphery, Carson’s,
542 Brown’s hypothesis, etc.). In a seminal publication, Brown (1984) introduced the abundant-
543 centre hypothesis. Although it refers explicitly to abundance patterns, it has been invoked to
544 underlie variation in other traits and population features in a centre–periphery context. In our
545 study, we restrict usage of this term to the specific domain of abundance. The word “margin”

546 has been used to refer to both ecological marginality (Soulé, 1973; Farris & Schaal, 1983) and
547 geographical marginality (Arana *et al.*, 2010; Doudová-Kochánková *et al.*, 2012). The latter is
548 confusing because geographical and ecological gradients are not necessarily concordant
549 (Soulé, 1973; Pironon *et al.*, 2015, see further discussion in Section V.1). For clarity, we
550 prescribe the use of the term ‘centre–periphery’ hypothesis when studying the geographical
551 distribution of genetic and demographic performance, and restrict the use of ‘central–
552 marginal’ gradients to strictly ecological considerations (Shreeve, Dennis & Pullin, 1996;
553 Hardie & Hutchings, 2010).

554

555 **(2) General results**

556 To analyse the number of tests that show significant differences between central and
557 peripheral populations for different traits and features, we retained studies with a geographical
558 centre–periphery approach and discarded those whose centre–periphery pattern relied solely
559 on population abundance or ecological gradients. This restricted the number of articles to 234,
560 representing 804 tests of the CPH.

561

562 *(a) Abundance*

563 The abundant-centre hypothesis (an offshoot of the general CPH) is based on two
564 assumptions: environmental variables are spatially correlated throughout a species range, and
565 abundance peaks where environmental conditions are best for the species considered, i.e. in
566 central populations (Brown, 1984; Sagarin *et al.*, 2006).

567 We found that population occupancy showed a strong trend towards lower values in
568 peripheral populations (81% of studied tests). However, this significant trend is based on only
569 21 tests in 15 papers (Table 1). Additionally, we noticed that several studies considered this
570 pattern as a fact and defined their centre–periphery sampling scheme based on this criterion.

571 For example, some genetic studies contrasted large and continuous central populations to
572 small and scattered peripheral populations (Jones & Gliddon, 1999; Van Rossum *et al.*, 2003;
573 Medrano & Herrera, 2008), although they did not measure any fragmentation or frequency of
574 populations.

575 69 out of 136 tests (51%) focusing on the abundance of individuals reported higher abundance
576 in the central part of the distribution. The trend is weaker than for occupancy patterns (Table
577 1) and does not support the abundant-centre hypothesis. Sagarin & Gaines (2002*b*) found
578 even weaker support for the hypothesis, but their study gave a high importance to a relatively
579 low number of papers (145 tests extracted from 22 papers, 39% of which provide support for
580 the abundant-centre hypothesis). In particular, the study by Blackburn *et al.* (1999*b*) alone
581 represented 44% of the total number of considered tests, and did not support the CPH. This
582 paper was not included in our study, as we were not able to identify central and peripheral
583 areas of the ranges of the different species considered.

584 Different results for population occupancy and abundance of individuals may be due to
585 differences in the factors shaping those patterns (Lawton, 1993; Hoffman & Blows, 1994;
586 Gaston, 1996, 2009; Thuiller, 2013), which may act over different scales (Gilbert, 1980;
587 Gilman, 2005; Boulangeat, Gravel & Thuiller, 2012). The strong spatial organization of
588 occupancy patterns may be primarily driven by climatic factors which act over a large scale
589 and are often spatially autocorrelated (Thuiller, Araújo & Lavorel, 2004). This is supported by
590 recent cross-taxa empirical analyses for both plants (Boucher-Lalonde, Morin & Currie, 2012)
591 and animals (Boucher-Lalonde, Morin & Currie, 2014). By contrast, variables linked to the
592 abundance of individuals could operate at more local scale (Pearson & Dawson, 2003;
593 Elmendorf & Moore, 2008) and exhibit low spatial structure (Caughley *et al.*, 1988; Lawton,
594 1993). For example, Gilman (2005) highlighted the importance of water temperature, tides,
595 wave force and biotic interactions in shaping the local abundance pattern of an intertidal

596 limpet (*Collisella scabra* Gould). The spatial layering of these ecological factors (Pearson &
597 Dawson, 2003) might explain range-wide clumped distributions of abundance of individuals
598 observed in some taxa (see Brown, Mehlman & Stevens, 1995), and lead to the low general
599 support for a large-scale decrease in abundance of individuals towards the periphery (Keitt *et*
600 *al.*, 2001). However, species might respond differently to these ecological factors due to their
601 diversity of life-history characteristics (Gaston, 2003).

602 Spatial and temporal variation in abundance of individuals is predicted to be higher at the
603 periphery under the CPH (Curnutt *et al.*, 1996; Sagarin *et al.*, 2006). This can be explained,
604 for example, by spatial patterns of habitat quality and their effect on source–sink models of
605 colonization, assuming that populations collapse after establishing in low-quality habitat
606 (Lawton, 1995; Curnutt *et al.*, 1996; Vucetich & Waite, 2003). Here, we only analysed 19
607 tests, and these exhibited no significant trend (Table 1); only one study showed higher
608 variability in the range centre (Law, 1994). Thus, the paucity of information regarding
609 variability remains an important gap in our understanding of range dynamics and the possible
610 occurrence of source–sink dynamics in peripheral populations (Pulliam, 1988, 2000; Curnutt
611 *et al.*, 1996).

612

613 *(b) Population performance*

614 Vital rates associated with population performance are predicted to decrease towards the
615 range periphery, and to become more variable (Sagarin *et al.*, 2006; Sexton *et al.*, 2009).
616 Lower fitness of peripheral populations due to unfavourable ecological conditions and/or
617 lower abundance could cause higher extinction probability and limit further colonization,
618 creating stable range limits (Holt & Keitt, 2000; Keitt *et al.*, 2001; Hardie & Hutchings, 2010;
619 Abeli *et al.*, 2014). However, for survival, growth, fecundity, recruitment, and overall
620 population growth rate, we found no consistent patterns that support this hypothesis: each

621 vital rate was equally likely to be higher in the centre, the periphery, or to exhibit no
622 difference (Table 1). This conclusion confirms results obtained by Sexton *et al.* (2009) and
623 Abeli *et al.* (2014). Range-wide studies of reproductive performance have reached similar
624 conclusions, emphasizing the important role of local environmental conditions on
625 demographic rates, which might blur their geographical patterns (Garcia, Goñi & Guzmán,
626 2010; Vilellas *et al.*, 2013a; Granado-Yela *et al.*, 2013).

627 Very few studies have evaluated the impact of abundance on population performance in a
628 centre–periphery context. Some reported higher performance in larger populations, through
629 higher fecundity and recruitment (Lemke & Porembski, 2013), or higher survival (Rodríguez
630 & Delibes, 2002), whereas others found no differences in demographic rates between small
631 and large populations (Berg, Becker & Matthies, 2005; Lester, Gaines & Kinlan, 2007).

632 Although many cases of the positive effects of large population size have been highlighted
633 (Reed, 2005), the association between population performance and abundance is not
634 unidirectional; negative density-dependence effects can also occur (Johnson *et al.*, 2012), and
635 some species have been shown to perform well at low population size (García, 2008).

636 Moreover, density-dependence effects might not always impact all demographic rates and/or
637 overall population growth rate (Kolb, Dahlgren & Ehrlén, 2010), and their intensity might
638 vary across a species range (Williams, Ives & Applegate, 2003). The presence, direction and
639 intensity or the absence of density dependence is just one of the many ecological factors
640 influencing demographic rates and could contribute to why these rates do not always follow a
641 centre–periphery pattern.

642 Individual size is also predicted to be lower in peripheral populations if they occur in less-
643 optimal ecological conditions (Meiri *et al.*, 2009). However, in the studies we reviewed, there
644 was no clear evidence of smaller individuals in peripheral populations: 55% of species
645 showed no differences across their range (Table 1). Other biogeographical studies have tried

646 to identify a theoretical link between organismal size and position in the geographic range,
647 among which Bergmann's rule predicts an increase in body size of endothermic animals with
648 higher latitudes, in order to limit energetic loss (Blackburn, Gaston & Loder, 1999a; Meiri,
649 2011). This linear increase is different from the hump-shaped scenario proposed by the CPH,
650 which suggests that the size of individuals might be driven by different mechanisms. In this
651 context, criticisms have been raised against the use of latitude as a proxy for harsher/colder
652 environmental conditions (Blackburn *et al.*, 1999a), which points to the need for a direct
653 estimate of the ecological drivers.

654 Finally, four articles (Siikamaki & Lammi, 1998; González-Guzmán & Mehlman, 2001; Kark
655 *et al.*, 2004; Vaupel & Matthies, 2012) dealt with the topic of developmental instability due to
656 strong directional selection or high inbreeding at range periphery (Levin, 1970). However, we
657 detected no difference in instability (measured as fluctuating asymmetry) between central and
658 peripheral populations. Thus, no global pattern of higher stress towards range edges appeared
659 in these studies (see also Parsons, 1990).

660

661 (c) *Genetic variation*

662 Several hypotheses have been proposed regarding the spatial organization of genetic variation
663 in the different parts of a species range (Safriel *et al.*, 1994; Hardie & Hutchings, 2010). One
664 of the predictions of the CPH is that within-population genetic diversity is lower in peripheral
665 than in central populations (Brussard, 1984; Eckert *et al.*, 2008). In our data set, 83 out of 175
666 tests (47%) showed this pattern (Table 1), which did not differ from a random expectation.
667 This contrasts with results obtained by a previous review (Eckert *et al.*, 2008), in which the
668 CPH was upheld in 65% of 68 studies. We investigated whether the support for the CPH
669 varied over time, and if it reflected changes in methods (see Appendix S4 for details). In our
670 data set, the variety of genetic methods used had no impact on the probability to detect a

671 centre–periphery pattern. However, temporal variations were detected. Before 2008, support
672 for the CPH (66%: 40/61 tests) was similar to that reported by Eckert *et al.* (2008). By
673 contrast, only 38% (43/114 tests) of studies done after 2008 provided support for the CPH,
674 resulting in a significant difference among temporal subsets of the dataset ($3 \times 2 \chi^2 = 13.8$, d.f.
675 = 2, $P < 0.001$). Thus, it is possible that recent studies integrated Eckert *et al.*'s (2008)
676 conclusion for the need to use a more representative sampling methodology to assess trends
677 across a greater proportion of the range, or to identify better the relative position of the
678 populations within the whole species' range (e.g. Diniz-Filho *et al.*, 2009; Dixon, Herlihy &
679 Busch, 2013). Additionally, most of the studies reviewed by Eckert *et al.* (2008) were
680 conducted at the leading edge of temperate species distributions, hence, they recommended
681 that other peripheral areas be examined in order to evaluate the general validity of the CPH
682 and disentangle the potential confounding effects of historical drivers from ongoing
683 contemporary processes. As they stated (p. 1171), “relatively few species exhibited consistent
684 geographical patterns in population genetic diversity towards different range edges [when
685 comparing] different studies”, illustrating a potential weakness of tests of the CPH
686 predictions. The post-2008 shift to more representative sampling is exemplified by the study
687 of Lira-Noriega & Manthey (2014). The authors collected genetic data from the literature
688 spanning most of the ranges of 40 plants and animals of different biogeographical origins, and
689 computed distances to the centroids of the species distributions. They found little global
690 support for the CPH.

691 In parallel, genetic differentiation is predicted to be higher among peripheral populations than
692 among central populations (Mayr, 1963; Eckert *et al.*, 2008). 33 out of 74 tests (45%) showed
693 this pattern (Table 1). This relationship was not different from a random expectation, and a
694 large number of tests found no differences. Again, this result contrasts with Eckert *et al.*'s
695 (2008) observations of higher differentiation among peripheral populations for 70% of studies

696 (40 studies out of 57), although the rate of support in their study decreased to 42% ($N = 26$)
697 when their test was restricted to publications performing statistical analyses of differentiation
698 values. Again, we found less support for the hypothesis in publications since 2008 ($\chi^2 = 8.5$,
699 d.f. = 2, $P = 0.01$). Methodological issues may add some confusion to the interpretation of
700 population differentiation across species range, because measures used to quantify it may be
701 biased by differences in genetic richness and distances among populations for central and
702 peripheral populations (Eckert *et al.*, 2008). The low rate of support we detected indicates that
703 empirical evidence does not globally support higher differentiation among populations at
704 range limits. Environmental differences (Lesica & Allendorf, 1995; Sexton *et al.*, 2014) and
705 metapopulation dynamics (Pannell & Charlesworth, 2000) may be more important
706 determinants of any such patterns (Endler, 1973).

707 Our study thus provides empirical evidence for an association between within-population
708 genetic diversity and among-population differentiation. Specifically, tests that exhibited
709 significantly lower within-population diversity in peripheral populations had a higher
710 probability of also showing an increase in genetic differentiation ($\chi^2 = 35.54$, d.f. = 4, $P <$
711 0.001). Genetically depauperate peripheral populations may thus be more prone to drift and
712 consequent genetic divergence (Eckert *et al.*, 2008; Leonardi *et al.*, 2012).

713 Finally, following the assumption of lower census and effective population size at range limits
714 (Vucetich & Waite, 2003), inbreeding is predicted to be higher in peripheral populations. Our
715 results did not deviate from random expectation, with 15 out of 31 tests (48%) reporting
716 higher inbreeding in peripheral populations (Table 1). Thus, this underlines the fact that
717 centre–periphery gradients did not coincide with patterns of variation in effective population
718 size across the range (Frankham, 2007), as mirrored by abundance of individuals and actual
719 population size (see Section IV.2a, b).

720 Finally, 22 tests used other approaches (e.g. karyology in Medail *et al.*, 2002; Rivero-Guerra,
721 2008) that we did not analyse quantitatively due to their heterogeneity.

722

723 **(3) Plant–animal differences**

724 Spatial patterns of genetic and demographic variation are strongly linked to the life-history
725 characteristics of organisms, such as longevity, competitive or dispersal abilities (Gaston,
726 2003). Therefore, genetic variation, abundance, and population performance patterns may
727 exhibit strong differences among groups (Gaston, 2003). Our data set is composed of a large
728 diversity of organisms including annual ($N = 31$) and perennial plants ($N = 171$), birds ($N =$
729 65), mammals ($N = 38$), insects ($N = 33$), fishes ($N = 13$), amphibians ($N = 10$), reptiles ($N =$
730 6) and marine invertebrates ($N = 44$) (Appendix S1). To investigate this issue, we tested
731 whether kingdom (plant or animal) influenced rates of support for the CPH.

732 For within-population genetic diversity, a marginally significant difference ($\chi^2 = 5.9$, d.f. = 2,
733 $P = 0.053$) was found between the two groups: 54% of tests conducted on plants provide
734 support for the CPH (54 out of 100 tests), while only 39% (29 out of 75 tests) fit this model
735 for tests conducted on animals (Table 2). However, when restricting our analysis to papers
736 that treat a single species, 56% of all animal- and plant-based tests provided support for the
737 CPH. The differential pattern was mainly driven by one multi-species article (Lira-Noriega &
738 Manthey, 2014), in which four plant species (out of 13) but only one out of 25 tests on
739 animals provided such support.

740 For population performance, no significant differences were detected between plants and
741 animals (Appendix S5).

742 For the abundance of individuals, only animals provide significant support for the CPH ($\chi^2 =$
743 22 , d.f. = 2, $P < 0.001$) (Table 2). This difference suggests that life-history traits affect
744 geographic patterns of variation in abundance. Svensson (1992) first proposed that the

745 abundant-centre hypothesis would be confirmed more often for animals than plants, based on
746 the sparse observations available at that time (Carter & Prince, 1981; Woods & Davis, 1989)
747 and without providing any theoretical explanation. In general, local ecological constraints
748 may strongly impact organisms with a sessile life form such as plants for which abundance
749 will be dependent on micro-ecological factors (Chapin *et al.*, 1987; Lammi, Siikamäki &
750 Mustajärvi, 1999; Lönn & Prentice, 2002; Nielsen *et al.*, 2005). These variables tend to
751 exhibit little geographic autocorrelation (Gilman, 2005), and therefore can blur geographic
752 variation in abundance. By contrast, for vagile animals, individual requirements in terms of
753 metabolic rates (Root, 1988) and the distribution of resources (Schluter & Repasky, 1991)
754 may be major drivers of abundance patterns. These environmental processes rely strongly on
755 climate, and thus are more coarsely spatially structured. In addition, resource limitation
756 generates competition in mobile animals promoting long-distance dispersal to new potentially
757 suitable sites (Curnutt *et al.*, 1996), with vagrant individuals frequently observed out of their
758 range (Grinnell, 1922). Although these sites may not fulfill the requirements for species to
759 establish populations (Pulliam, 2000), they may tend to enlarge the array of ecological
760 conditions encountered by the species *in natura*, and lead individuals to face harsher
761 conditions at range margins (Hargreaves *et al.*, 2014). Hence source–sink dynamics would be
762 more common and spatially structured in vagrant animals than in plants, which fits the
763 predictions of the theoretical model of Guo *et al.* (2005). Ultimately, understanding
764 abundance patterns and in particular the spatial structure and density of sink populations
765 towards range edges would provide key information on the limits to species ranges (Sexton *et*
766 *al.*, 2009).

767

768 **(4) Limitations associated with sampling methods**

769 Several authors have discussed the importance of methodological biases in studies testing the
770 CPH, especially the failure adequately to sample central and peripheral parts of a species
771 range (Eckert *et al.*, 2008). As a result, this may hinder generalization on the validity of the
772 CPH (Sagarin & Gaines, 2002*b*). Indeed, the shape and size of species ranges can vary
773 dramatically among taxa and thus affect the expression of variation in demographic and
774 genetic characteristics (Gaston, 2003). Thus, we analyse two spatial patterns. First,
775 geographic isolation of peripheral populations is supposed to limit colonization events and
776 consequently slow down metapopulation dynamics (Gilpin & Hanski, 1991) and affect
777 genetic patterns across species' ranges (Hastings & Harrison, 1994). In our database, only
778 11% of all tests considered a periphery beyond the main range; 42% sampled peripheral
779 populations at the very edge of the range, while 45% considered populations clearly located
780 within the main range of the species as peripheral populations. Second, the majority of species
781 distribution ranges exceed individual dispersal abilities, hence populations in different parts of
782 the range are fairly isolated from one another, at least over the short term (Wright, 1943;
783 Hardy & Vekemans, 1999). Therefore, range size may condition the frequency of interactions
784 among populations, and the representativeness of the sample in terms of the global
785 distribution of the species may affect its power to capture such processes. In our pool of
786 papers, 28% of all tests considered less than 10% of the range of the species, and 26% studied
787 10–50% of the range. Hence, only 44% of all tests were conducted over more than 50% of the
788 species' ranges. Most studies (56%) thus identify central populations that, with an expanded
789 sampling scheme, could be considered as peripheral. The strong correlation that we found
790 between 'representativeness' and 'spatial extent of the study' showed that studies carried out
791 at a larger scale tend to be more representative of the global range extent of species. Based on
792 this finding, we use a composite variable 'scale' that synthesizes both measures.

793 For the abundance of individuals, we found that spatial ‘scale’ had a significant positive
794 impact on the rate of support for the CPH (Table 3). Thus, studies that encompassed more
795 than 50% of a species distribution and that were conducted at a large scale (continental) were
796 more likely to detect a reduced abundance of individuals in peripheral populations, as
797 envisioned previously by Sagarin *et al.* (2006). Choosing representative central and peripheral
798 populations might thus increase the probability of sampling less-optimal ecological conditions
799 at the periphery of a species distribution (Sagarin & Gaines, 2002*b*). However, this result may
800 also be influenced by a small number of studies on multiple bird species (representing a high
801 number of tests), that showed a pattern that strongly supports the CPH and that had a more
802 range-wide sampling than studies of plants (for plant–animal comparison, $\chi^2 = 5.03$, d.f. = 2,
803 $P = 0.08$). Thus, the pattern should be interpreted with caution, and large-scale studies should
804 be applied to plants to disentangle the effect of organism and scale at which studies are
805 conducted. It is also worth noticing that spatial isolation had no impact on abundance patterns,
806 which highlights that peripheral isolates might occur in suitable environmental conditions that
807 allow the establishment of viable populations.

808 For population performance, the absence of any impact of the variables ‘scale’ and ‘isolation’
809 reinforces their relative independence from the extent of the geographical gradient (Table 3).
810 However, studies with larger sampling schemes were more likely to exhibit an absence of
811 difference in recruitment across the range. This is in accordance with previous results that
812 emphasized the importance of local variables that exhibit little spatial structure (Connolly,
813 Menge & Roughgarden, 2001; Granado-Yela *et al.*, 2013; Ibáñez & McCarthy-Neumann,
814 2014). However, this does not support the proposition that isolated populations show a
815 decrease in population performance due to slower metapopulation dynamics (Holt & Keitt,
816 2000).

817 For genetic diversity, we found a strong positive impact of peripheral isolation on the rate of
818 support for the CPH, which highlighted the importance of current range structure on genetic
819 diversity (Table 3) (Holt, 2003; Leonardi *et al.*, 2012). Indeed, this validation rate decreased
820 from 70% ($N_{\text{test}} = 35$) to 61% ($N_{\text{test}} = 61$) to 42% ($N_{\text{test}} = 83$) when considering peripheral
821 isolates out of the range, absolute peripheries and intermediate peripheries, respectively.
822 Peripheral isolation will slow down metapopulation dynamics and limit gene flow among
823 populations (Holt & Keitt, 2000; Holt, 2003; Böhme *et al.*, 2007). In addition, studies that
824 used population size to define their centre–periphery gradient brought evidence for a positive
825 impact of population size on genetic diversity: 10 out of 14 tests found a higher genetic
826 diversity in larger populations (e.g. Lammi *et al.*, 1999; Dostálek, Münzbergová & Plačková,
827 2014), whereas four of them did not find differences (e.g. Michalski & Durka, 2007; but see
828 Wood, Yates & Fraser, 2016). Besides the impact of isolation, a nearly significant effect of
829 scale suggested a greater decrease of genetic diversity when considering larger spatial scales.
830 This suggests that there may be a trend for genetic diversity to decrease gradually from the
831 centre to the periphery, but it requires large-scale sampling to capture it. This could be
832 consistent with the footprint of repeated founder events following post-glacial range
833 expansion (e.g. Cwynar & MacDonald, 1987; Dudaniec *et al.*, 2012), which have an impact
834 on large-scale patterns, and might be strongly dependent on species history (Hewitt, 2000;
835 Petit *et al.*, 2003). As a result, genetic diversity will be shaped by both contemporary factors
836 and historical events, the relative importance of which may be species-specific (Hampe &
837 Petit, 2005; Kropf, 2012).

838 Genetic differentiation was strongly linked to the physical isolation of peripheral populations
839 (Table 3). This observation suggests that gene flow among populations decreases toward the
840 range edge depending on peripheral isolation (Leonardi *et al.*, 2012; Wang, Glor & Losos,
841 2013). However, the absence of any effect of the variable ‘scale’ pinpoints the relative

842 independence from the spatial extent of the study (Table 3). This indicates that genetic
843 differentiation does not follow a simple isolation by distance process, in which gene flow is
844 inversely proportional to distance among populations (Sexton *et al.*, 2014).
845 Overall, the decrease in genetic diversity and increase in genetic differentiation observed for
846 isolated peripheral populations do not support predictions of theoretical models of
847 asymmetrical gene flow (Kirkpatrick & Barton, 1997). However, spatial variation in neutral
848 markers may poorly reflect quantitative genetic variation that would permit a population to
849 adapt (Reed & Frankham, 2001; Blows & Hoffmann, 2005). Hence, little is known regarding
850 the adaptive potential of peripheral populations (Eckert *et al.*, 2008) and whether the lack of
851 adaptation contributes to range limits (but see Blows & Hoffman, 1993; Magiafoglou &
852 Hoffmann, 2003; Kellermann *et al.*, 2006).

853

854 **V. GEOGRAPHICALLY PERIPHERAL OR ECOLOGICALLY MARGINAL?**

855 **(1) Are peripheral populations ecologically marginal?**

856 A major tenet of the CPH is that a species distribution is a geographical representation of its
857 ecological niche (*sensu* Hutchinson, 1957) with environmental conditions optimal at the range
858 centre and poorer at the periphery (Brown, 1984; Hoffman & Blows, 1994; Holt & Keitt,
859 2000). However, it has been argued that “not all marginal populations are peripherally located
860 and not all peripheral populations are ecologically marginal” (Soulé, 1973, p. 165; see also
861 Hardie & Hutchings, 2010). If such concordance between geographical and environmental
862 centre–periphery gradients is proven wrong, then the pertinence of further predictions
863 associated with the CPH could be challenged. Although essential, this assumption is often
864 overlooked when testing the CPH: only 17% (42 studies) of our pool of 248 papers
865 quantitatively evaluated ecological conditions (biotic and/or abiotic) in central and peripheral
866 locations (Fig. 1B, “Ecology”).

867 Of these 42 studies (82 tests), 34 (81%) compared environmental variables in central and
868 peripheral populations (i.e. ‘environment’); five papers compared spatial or temporal variation
869 of these variables (i.e. ‘environmental variability’), and only three considered measures of
870 both environment and environmental variability. In general, the authors considered a wide
871 variety of environmental variables: 17 studies (40%) examined abiotic variables (e.g. climate,
872 soil properties), 16 (39%) considered biotic variables (e.g. mutualism, predation,
873 competition), and nine studies (21%) examined both biotic and abiotic environmental
874 variables. Overall, we found that 62% of the 82 tests on the environment reported different
875 environmental conditions between central and peripheral populations (‘Different’ in Fig. 3).
876 Although this result is highly dependent on the choice of the environmental variable, it
877 supports the notion that species encounter different ecological conditions at their range limits.
878 This is not surprising given the low probability of finding exactly the same conditions in two
879 different areas.

880 In the 82 tests, 57 provided data that allowed us to examine whether the environment is
881 optimal (i.e. more suitable) in central populations compared to peripheral populations
882 (‘Optimal’ in Fig. 3), optimality being defined according to the presence (*versus* absence) of
883 natural enemies (e.g. Briers, 2003), pollinators (e.g. Lemke & Porembski, 2013), a higher
884 climatic suitability (e.g. Diniz-Filho *et al.*, 2009), or food availability (e.g. Gilman, 2006b).
885 Despite the fact that environmental conditions are different in central and peripheral
886 populations, there is no evidence that environmental quality is systematically lower at the
887 periphery of a species’ distribution (Fig. 3). For instance, Lira-Noriega & Manthey (2014)
888 found positive correlations between distances from populations to species’ geographic range
889 centres and climatic niche centroids in only 16 out of their 37 tests (43%). These results are in
890 line with previous studies that showed that the different environmental variables required by
891 the species were not distributed continuously across its range but instead showed more

892 discrete variation (Poulin & Dick, 2007; Hidas, Ayre & Minchinton, 2010; Baldanzi *et al.*,
893 2013), and that habitats at the geographical range limits were not always less suitable for the
894 species (Chardon *et al.*, 2014; Hargreaves *et al.*, 2014). In a study of 11 Mediterranean plant
895 species, G. Papuga, P. Gauthier, J. Ramos, V. Pons, E. Farris & J.D. Thompson (in
896 preparation) also show multiple ecological differences between central and peripheral
897 populations. But again, there is no evidence that such differences involve a change in habitat
898 quality.

899 Our results thus reject the hypothesis that geographical and ecological gradients are
900 systematically associated with one another and that peripheral populations are always
901 ecologically marginal. Ecologically optimal sites can be found across most species ranges
902 (Poulin & Dick, 2007). In addition, peripheral populations might preferentially occupy sites
903 where the environment is locally favourable for the species (Lennon *et al.*, 2002; Thompson
904 *et al.*, 2010), even though such locations are less common near the range limits. However,
905 little is known about whether the availability of high-quality sites generally increases towards
906 the centre of the range (González-Guzmán & Mehlman, 2001; Murphy, VanDerWal &
907 Lovett-Doust, 2006). The presence of such geographical structure might depend mainly on the
908 relative influence of highly spatially autocorrelated variables, such as climate. Further
909 comparative studies are now needed on the distribution of spatial and temporal variation in
910 environmental suitability across species ranges.

911

912 **(2) Ecological marginality and genetic and demographic variation**

913 We have shown that the literature does not illustrate a strict and consistent concordance
914 between geographical and ecological gradients. Hence, it is important to test whether trait
915 variation in different parts of a geographic range is actually associated with spatial variation
916 in ecological conditions. In our pool of 248 studies, only 54 (22%) measured ecological

917 conditions at different sites (geographically central/peripheral or not) and simultaneously
918 assessed one or other of the above categories of species traits and population features (genetic
919 diversity, abundance, population performance, size). 21 out of these 54 papers clearly
920 identified environmental conditions of higher and lower suitability for the species (e.g. Lönn
921 & Prentice, 2002; Gilman, 2006b; Lira-Noriega & Manthey, 2014), whereas 33 just
922 considered ecological gradients without indications as to species preferences (e.g. Howes &
923 Lougheed, 2008; Stanton-Geddes, Shaw & Tiffin, 2012a). To have a sufficiently high sample
924 size of studies, we therefore focused on whether species perform differently in regions that
925 currently present clear ecological differences (without analysing whether such differences
926 involve enhanced performance in more favourable conditions). For the same reason, we also
927 considered only four broad categories of species traits and population features (genetic
928 diversity, abundance, population performance, size) (Fig. 4). When a paper studied different
929 features on the same species (e.g. survival and fecundity in the ‘population performance’
930 category), we considered these tests separately. Finally, it is also worth noting that we only
931 focused on the literature related to the CPH and that many other studies have focused on
932 responses of different genetic or demographic features across environmental gradients (e.g.
933 Doak & Morris, 2010; Manel *et al.*, 2012). Future reviews or analyses of these studies could
934 help refine our conclusions.

935 First, we found that 62% of tests did not exhibit any difference in genetic diversity between
936 populations occurring in different environmental conditions (Fig. 4). Some studies observed
937 differences in genetic diversity across climatic gradients (e.g. Howes & Lougheed, 2008;
938 Moeller, Geber & Tiffin, 2011) and some did not (e.g. Shulgina *et al.*, 2006; Diniz-Filho *et al.*,
939 2009). Other articles found differences across habitats (e.g. Shumaker & Babble, 1980;
940 Hamilton & Eckert, 2007) and others did not (e.g. Van Rossum *et al.*, 2003). However, a
941 recent meta-analysis showed that the distance to climatic niche centroids better explained the

942 distribution of the genetic diversity of 40 plant and animal species than the distance to their
943 geographic range centres (Lira-Noriega & Manthey, 2014). That said, the authors argued that
944 current ecological conditions may not directly affect within-population genetic diversity, but
945 rather act through indirect effects such as changes in effective population size, gene flow, or
946 population stability through time. Here, the temporal dynamics of ecological conditions might
947 have a greater impact than current static conditions. For instance, many studies have shown
948 that current spatial patterns of genetic variation have been shaped by past climate change *via*
949 changes in species occurrence and/or abundance (Hewitt, 2000; Carnaval *et al.*, 2009;
950 Excoffier, Foll, & Petit, 2009; Hoban *et al.*, 2010; Pironon *et al.*, 2015; see further discussion
951 in Section VI). However, contemporary effects of isolation by environment might directly
952 shape distributional patterns of genetic variation for some species presenting relatively stable
953 distributions over time (e.g. some Mediterranean, tropical, or small-range species less
954 impacted by glaciations) (Ortego *et al.*, 2012; Sexton *et al.*, 2014).

955 By contrast, ecological gradients may be related to differences in abundance, demographic
956 rates and size (Fig. 4). Indeed, most studies reported associations between these features and
957 climate (e.g. Crozier, 2004), or habitat type (e.g. Stanton-Geddes *et al.*, 2012a; Huntsman &
958 Petty, 2014). Moreover, several studies that were able to identify species preferences reported
959 enhanced performance in areas less disturbed by humans (Fuller *et al.*, 2009), with more
960 suitable substrate conditions (Lönn & Prentice, 2002), or with higher food supply (Gilman,
961 2006b). In addition, several recent analyses have found a positive relationship between plant
962 and animal species abundances and environmental (mainly climatic) suitability and have thus
963 tried to affirm the validity of the central–marginal model (VanDerWal *et al.*, 2009; Oliver *et*
964 *al.*, 2012; Martínez-Meyer *et al.*, 2013; Van Couwenberghe *et al.*, 2013).

965 If ecological conditions are distributed discretely (rather than continuously) in geographical
966 space (see section V.1), demographic performance might follow a multimodal distribution

967 (rather than a simple gradient), as proposed by the ‘local-oasis model’ (Poulin & Dick, 2007)
968 and described by other studies (Murphy *et al.*, 2006; Baldanzi *et al.*, 2013, but see also Keitt
969 *et al.*, 2001). However, we previously found that population occupancy matched the CPH
970 predictions better than the abundance of individuals, which in turn provides more support for
971 the CPH than other demographic rates (e.g. survival, growth) (see Section IV.2). The relative
972 influence of geographical and ecological gradients may thus be scale dependent: the impact of
973 geography might decrease from broad (i.e. population occupancy) to fine scale (i.e.
974 demographic rates), whereas the effect of local ecological conditions might increase
975 (Hoffmann & Blows, 1994). Although more studies are needed to confirm such trends,
976 population occupancy may be related to a decreasing availability of highly suitable sites from
977 the range centre to the periphery, whereas the abundance of individuals and other
978 demographic rates may be high in highly suitable sites found both at the centre and the
979 periphery of the species range (see V.1). Finally, the different components of demographic
980 performance (abundance and other vital rates) could be influenced by different ecological
981 factors (e.g. climate, habitat, biotic interactions), and these relationships may vary among
982 species (Pironon *et al.*, 2015; Vilellas *et al.*, 2015). Some recent studies have proposed the
983 concept of ‘demographic compensation’ by demonstrating that vital rates of one species might
984 often follow opposing patterns along geographical and/or environmental gradients (Doak &
985 Morris, 2010; Vilellas *et al.*, 2015). All in all, there remains the important and challenging
986 task to identify which environmental dimensions better predict the distribution of these
987 components for different species (Boulangéat *et al.*, 2012; Ehrlén & Morris, 2015).

988 In this context, species distribution models (SDMs) represent one of the most commonly used
989 tools in biogeography (Elith & Leathwick 2009). These correlative statistical models project
990 species potential distributions in space and time by relating field observations of their
991 occurrence to environmental predictor variables. The accuracy of SDMs has been questioned

992 and several limitations have been raised (Elith & Leathwick, 2009), primarily in relation to
993 the fact that they do not rely on the biological processes that underlie species persistence, but
994 rather on simple correlations (Kearney & Porter, 2009; Buckley *et al.*, 2010). Recent studies
995 have therefore highlighted the need to incorporate demographic, functional, phenological, or
996 evolutionary information into SDMs (Buckley & Kingsolver, 2012; Ehrlén & Morris, 2015).
997 Although simple correlative SDMs may capture geographical variation in abundance
998 relatively well (VanDerWal *et al.*, 2009; Oliver *et al.*, 2012; Boulangeat *et al.*, 2012; Van
999 Couwenberghe *et al.*, 2013), they may not reflect population performance (Thuiller *et al.*,
1000 2015). Novel process-based approaches are now being developed to account more directly for
1001 the spatial (and temporal) variation in local population dynamics (Pagel & Schurr, 2012;
1002 Merow *et al.*, 2014; Zurell *et al.*, 2016). These developments could improve our
1003 understanding of the distribution of both demographic performance and species occurrence.

1004

1005 **VI. CENTRE-PERIPHERY OR REAR-LEADING EDGE?**

1006 **(1) Disentangling the dichotomy**

1007 There is much debate concerning whether geographic patterns of variation in species
1008 characteristics are driven by the current shape of their range (i.e. contemporary connectivity
1009 among populations) (Johansson, Primmer & Merilae, 2006) or by historical processes
1010 associated with past environmental change such as post-glacial recolonization and/or human
1011 activities (Hewitt, 2000; Channell & Lomolino, 2000; Excoffier *et al.*, 2009). Disentangling
1012 the relative impacts of contemporary and historical drivers is thus important, and there is a
1013 growing interest in the documentation of rear- *versus* leading-edge effects that provide a more
1014 dynamic explanation for patterns otherwise attributed to a static contemporary centre–
1015 periphery contrast (Hampe & Petit, 2005; Eckert *et al.*, 2008; Pironon *et al.*, 2015).

1016 In our pool of 248 papers, we have very little information on the past distributions of most of
1017 the studied species. For this reason, we first used the proxy ‘latitude/altitude’ to define what
1018 may have been historical central and peripheral parts of the species’ ranges. Many species
1019 have in fact been shown to follow latitudinal/altitudinal gradients when contracting or
1020 expanding their ranges during the alternation of glacial cycles, particularly temperate species
1021 (Hewitt, 2000). Moreover, considering both central–peripheral and latitudinal gradients
1022 together has been shown to be of particular importance for understanding patterns of genetic
1023 diversity across current species distributions (Guo, 2012). We thus make the assumption that
1024 all species present older and more stable populations at low latitude/altitude and younger
1025 populations at high latitude/altitude (Hampe & Petit, 2005).

1026 To study this issue, we discarded studies monitoring populations on longitudinal, ecological,
1027 or abundance-related gradients. In each of the 220 remaining studies (565 tests), we examined
1028 whether the genetic or demographic traits under consideration showed two potential trends.
1029 First, we examined whether species showed either an increase (P in Fig. 5), a decrease (C), or
1030 no significant change (N) from the current range centre (i.e. mid-latitude/altitude) towards the
1031 actual range periphery (i.e. higher and/or lower latitudes/altitudes). Second, we examined
1032 whether species show either an increase (H in Fig. 5), a decrease (L) or no significant change
1033 (N) from the historical range centre (i.e. low latitude/altitude) towards the periphery (i.e. high
1034 latitude/altitude). These comparisons allowed us to identify nine different scenarios based on
1035 the percentage of tests which provide support for each of them (Fig. 5). Obviously, all of the
1036 220 studies did not intend to test for such latitudinal/altitudinal relationships, so this
1037 information is based on our interpretation of trends described in each paper.

1038 First, the scenario of no variation across the range (N–N, lower-right scenario in Fig. 5A) is
1039 always overrepresented because, unlike other scenarios, it combines both range-wide studies
1040 and articles studying only one range periphery. Then, we found that, whatever the

1041 genetic/demographic trait considered, most studies were conducted at only one range
1042 periphery (four upper-left scenarios in Fig. 5A), and especially at the high latitude/altitude
1043 periphery (upper-left and middle scenarios in Fig. 5A). It is thus not possible to discriminate
1044 in those studies the potential contributions of historical and contemporary causes of current
1045 geographic patterns. These results therefore expose the need for more range-wide conjoint
1046 studies of spatial genetic variation and demographic performance.

1047 Also, the results confirm our finding that the geographical structure of species ranges is more
1048 closely associated with genetic variation and population occupancy than with the abundance
1049 of individuals and the different components of population performance (Table 1, Fig. 5).

1050 While there is no difference in the size of individuals between central and peripheral
1051 populations, or between low and high latitude/altitude populations (N–N scenario in Fig. 5),
1052 demographic rates (survival, growth, fecundity, and recruitment) respond in many different
1053 directions without exhibiting a particular tendency for the centre–periphery or the rear–
1054 leading edge model. Indeed, it is unlikely that historical range shifts impact current individual
1055 size and demographic rates (Pironon *et al.*, 2015), except for cases of very recent changes in
1056 species distribution, e.g. invasive species (Kilkenny & Galloway, 2013).

1057 Only 19 tests investigated the distribution of population occupancy, and most of these studies
1058 were conducted in the higher latitude/altitude range half, which impedes the detection of any
1059 differences between centre–periphery and rear–leading edge effects. On the other hand, more
1060 cases of ‘no variation’ across the range were registered for the abundance of individuals.

1061 Again, most of the papers only studied one half of the range (at high latitude/altitude) but,
1062 when a pattern was found at low latitude/altitude or across the whole range, it seemed to
1063 provide more support for the CPH than the rear-leading edge interpretation (‘abundance’ in
1064 Fig. 5B). The long-term dynamics of species ranges are therefore very unlikely to have an
1065 effect on current species abundance, contrary to original predictions (Adams, 1902). As

1066 suggested by other studies (Cowles, 1901; Transeau, 1903; Martínez-Meyer *et al.*, 2013; Van
1067 Couwenberghe *et al.*, 2013) and our previous results (see Section V.2), the contemporary
1068 distribution of ecological conditions seems to have a stronger impact.

1069 Finally, within-population genetic diversity decreases from the centre towards the high
1070 latitude/altitude edge of many species, and genetic differentiation frequently increases (Fig. 5)
1071 especially when the former is the case (see Section IV.2c). However, although the CPH seems
1072 to find more support than the rear–leading edge hypothesis for ‘genetic diversity’ and ‘genetic
1073 differentiation’ (Fig. 5B), what shapes the distribution of genetic variation across the species
1074 range, particularly towards low latitude/altitude, remains rather unclear. Rear-edge
1075 populations are probably impacted by different environmental factors than leading-edge
1076 populations. For instance, it has been suggested that they may potentially be undergoing a
1077 stronger effect from local environmental factors such as biotic interactions, and a less-limiting
1078 effect of regional climate (Schemske *et al.*, 2009; Louthan *et al.*, 2015) although this pattern
1079 has been contradicted by recent studies (Cunningham *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, rear-edge
1080 populations have generally been more stable over the short (Parmesan *et al.*, 1999) and the
1081 long term (Hewitt, 2000), which might contribute to their higher genetic diversity (Hampe &
1082 Petit, 2005). This is probably particularly true for rear-edge populations that occur in known
1083 refugia during periods of Quaternary glaciation. Nevertheless, little is known regarding the
1084 impact of current and past habitat fragmentation on the genetic structure of rear-edge
1085 populations (but see Sexton, Strauss & Rice, 2011, Sexton *et al.*, 2014). As highlighted
1086 previously by Hampe & Petit (2005), “the rear edge matters” and more investigations on rear-
1087 edge populations (and on the whole species range, from the rear to the leading edge) would
1088 help to understand how species can cope with future climate and land-use change, as well as
1089 to refine the predictions of the CPH.

1090

1091 **(2) Historical range dynamics**

1092 We extracted from our pool of papers the 22 studies (22 tests) that purposefully tested for
1093 differences in genetic diversity between clearly identified refugia and areas of post-glacial
1094 recolonization (Fig. 6). Evidence for historical range shifts were obtained in relation to the
1095 known past distribution of the ice sheet (e.g. Dolan, 1994; Hoban *et al.*, 2010; Stone *et al.*,
1096 2012), climatic reconstructions of species distributions at the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM)
1097 (e.g. Fuchs *et al.*, 2013; Gassert *et al.*, 2013), or through fossil dating (e.g. Cwynar &
1098 MacDonald, 1987). 16 of the 22 selected tests (73%) showed lower genetic diversity in
1099 potentially younger, recolonizing populations relative to potentially older populations
1100 (refugia). Although there is no perfect match, the latitudinal/altitudinal gradient tends to
1101 follow the direction of species recolonization after glaciations, at least for temperate species.
1102 This is not pertinent for species that may have had high- or mid-latitude refugia, such as
1103 tropical species (Nunes, Norris & Knowlton, 2009; Fuchs *et al.*, 2013).

1104 Another interesting result here is that the CPH is only confirmed for nine out of the 22 tests
1105 (41%; Fig. 6). Centre–periphery and rear–leading edge gradients are therefore not always
1106 concordant, and the latter, when clearly identified and not only based on a latitudinal proxy,
1107 appears to represent a major driver of the geographic structure of genetic diversity in many
1108 species. Although our analysis is based on a relatively small number of studies (22), several
1109 recent papers have also supported this view (Duncan *et al.*, 2015; Pironon *et al.*, 2015;
1110 Roberts & Hamann, 2015; Diniz-Filho *et al.*, 2016). However, we cannot conclude that
1111 contemporary geography of species ranges has no effect and that history acts alone (see
1112 Section IV.4). In fact, both historical and contemporary factors no doubt act to shape spatial
1113 patterns of genetic diversity (Guo, 2012).

1114 Regarding genetic differentiation, only 14 tests could be used for such analysis, which prevent
1115 us from making general conclusions. However, seven of these tests found lower

1116 differentiation among populations in areas that once served as refugia ('glaciation'), and only
1117 two reported lower differentiation among central populations ('centre/periphery'). Overall,
1118 our study highlights the need for more systematic studies disentangling the relative effects of
1119 contemporary and historical factors on the distribution of species' genetic variation. Past
1120 refugial areas are not always located at the centre of current species ranges, hence the
1121 importance of prudence when making tests of the CPH in a historical context.

1122

1123 **(3) The effect of species chorology**

1124 Finally, we classified all species into one of four chorological classes based on the bioregions
1125 they inhabit: boreal/tundra, temperate, Mediterranean, and tropical. Again, we evaluated
1126 whether species features responded to a centre–periphery (longitudinal studies were included
1127 this time to increase sample size) or a latitudinal/altitudinal gradient. Studies considering non-
1128 geographical centre–periphery gradients were discarded, as well as those considering marine
1129 species (too few for reliable comparisons). The number of studies analysing population
1130 occupancy and performance was too low to allow comparisons, so we focused on the study of
1131 abundance of individuals and genetic traits. For genetic differentiation and abundance of
1132 individuals, we did not find any significant differences among biogeographical groups
1133 (Appendix S6). Although sample sizes were very low for some regions, this result tends to
1134 confirm that there is no general support for the CPH in terms of these traits. Irrespective of the
1135 species' chorology, historical processes (past range shifts) do not appear to have driven
1136 current patterns in species abundance, and the causes of the distribution of genetic
1137 differentiation still remain unclear. By contrast, we found different distribution patterns for
1138 genetic diversity for species of different biogeographic origins (Fig. 7).
1139 Many temperate species have expanded or shifted their ranges from low to high latitudes
1140 since the LGM (Hewitt, 2000), and their genetic diversity reflects past range shifts (Fig. 6),

1141 therefore we would expect latitudinal/altitudinal gradients to provide a higher confirmation
1142 rate than a simple central–peripheral gradient. However, 31 out of 64 tests (48%) conducted
1143 on temperate species found a centre–periphery distribution of genetic diversity, and a very
1144 similar proportion found a latitudinal/altitudinal pattern (24 tests out of 45; 53%). As we saw
1145 previously, most of these studies were conducted at the high latitude/altitude range limit and
1146 we are therefore not able to disentangle centre–periphery from rear–leading edge effects (Fig.
1147 5). In addition, latitude might not always reflect the effects of range history, even in the case
1148 of temperate species. For instance, many North American species have followed east–west
1149 routes of recolonization (Williams *et al.*, 2004), which might affect the relevance of a
1150 latitudinal proxy. Moreover, within-population genetic diversity of many temperate taxa has
1151 been shown to reach maximum values at intermediate latitudes, due to the admixture of
1152 divergent lineages coming from distinct low-latitude macrorefugia (Petit *et al.*, 2003) or
1153 cryptic high-latitude refugia (Stewart & Lister, 2001). Although genetic diversity of temperate
1154 species often follows latitudinal gradients, this pattern cannot be generalized and will depend
1155 on how each species distribution has been impacted by past environmental changes.
1156 Boreal/tundra species exhibited a similar rate of support for the CPH (50%) to that of
1157 temperate species, but their genetic diversity was less likely to follow a latitudinal/altitudinal
1158 gradient (only 29% of studies provide support for the CPH). The distribution of boreal/tundra
1159 species has not been impacted by glaciations in the same way as for temperate species.
1160 Indeed, many might have subsisted in macrorefugia (e.g. Beringia refugium) or cryptic
1161 localized refugia (e.g. nunataks) at very high latitudes/altitudes (Abbott *et al.*, 2000; Shafer *et*
1162 *al.*, 2010), or may no longer have a rear edge at low latitude (Williams *et al.*, 2004).
1163 Populations of higher genetic diversity might therefore be located at the crossroads of
1164 different recolonization routes, often (but not always) positioned at the centre of the current
1165 range of the species.

1166 Finally, very few studies (<20 tests) have been conducted on Mediterranean or tropical
1167 species. Only seven tests out of 18 (39%) provide support for the CPH in Mediterranean taxa,
1168 whereas 11 out of 19 tests (58%) provide support for the CPH in tropical species.
1169 Latitude/altitude do not seem to explain better the distribution of genetic diversity of these
1170 taxa, especially for tropical species, for which only one test out of 14 found higher values at
1171 low latitude/altitude. Mediterranean and tropical species are particularly interesting because
1172 their historical ranges have been impacted very differently than temperate or boreal/tundra
1173 taxa. Indeed, the ice sheet never arrived at such low latitudes during peak glaciation, so the
1174 impact on their historical ranges will not have been to the extent observed for temperate
1175 species (Ortego *et al.*, 2012). Nevertheless, climate and topography have changed through
1176 time in these regions (Fauquette *et al.*, 2006; Claussen *et al.*, 2013) and the genetic legacy of
1177 ice ages can be detected in tropical and subtropical species, but not particularly on gradients
1178 of latitude (Diadema *et al.*, 2005; Carnaval *et al.*, 2009; Fuchs *et al.*, 2013). Genetic diversity
1179 in these species does not follow systematic central–peripheral or latitudinal patterns, but
1180 rather reflects the specific localized temporal dynamics of suitable environmental conditions.
1181 More investigations should be conducted on these particular biogeographical groups (e.g.
1182 Diniz-Filho *et al.*, 2016; Papuga *et al.*, 2015) if we are to reduce the overrepresentation of
1183 studies conducted at the northern range limit of temperate taxa – as highlighted previously
1184 (Eckert *et al.*, 2008).

1185

1186 **VII. SYNTHESIS AND PERSPECTIVES**

1187 The study of the CPH has a long history. Although this hypothesis may have at first sight a
1188 rather simple nature, its study has involved diverse types of approaches, often based on
1189 different conceptual issues, the study of a whole range of organisms whose life history traits
1190 can differentially influence how organisms disperse and respond to peripheral situations and,

1191 in recent years, a more dynamic historical approach to range limits. Herein, we have
1192 attempted to weave these different threads into a single synthesis of how species may show
1193 geographic patterns of variation in relation to their occurrence in peripheral populations. In
1194 addition, as a result of the plurality of the notions of centre and periphery, the CPH
1195 framework tends to mix a high diversity of underlying spatial, ecological, and/or historical
1196 processes into one single approach, based on a geographical gradient, to explain the
1197 distribution of several components of intraspecific variation (Eckert *et al.*, 2008; Pironon *et*
1198 *al.*, 2015). It is thus perhaps not surprising that the overall and very clear finding of our
1199 exhaustive study is that in general only around 50% of studies actually find support for the
1200 CPH, which thus does not represent a general rule for the different species traits we have
1201 examined.

1202 Our review highlights that the different components of genetic and demographic performance
1203 do not always exhibit a similar centre–periphery distributional pattern and, importantly, that
1204 instead of simple direct effects of changes in traits in peripheral situations of the range there
1205 may be a network of interacting effects on species traits and population features. We thus
1206 argue that the CPH needs to be reframed in relation to the potential effects of the interactions
1207 between geographical and ecological factors, between contemporary and historical range
1208 limits, and among different demographic and genetic traits. To do so, we propose a novel
1209 framework for future work (Fig. 8) that does not pretend to provide a new biogeographical
1210 law valid for all species, but emphasizes the need to adopt an integrated approach to the study
1211 of geographic variation. Identifying improvements to this framework will help refine
1212 predictions of the distribution of genetic and demographic performance.

1213 As suggested by our results (Section V.1) and several previous analyses (Chardon *et al.*, 2014;
1214 Lira-Noriega & Manthey, 2014; Hargreaves *et al.*, 2014), the major assumption on which the
1215 CPH is based, i.e. a concordance between geographical periphery and ecological marginality

1216 is satisfied far less often than most studies imply. There is simply no systematic gradual
1217 decrease in environmental suitability from the centre towards the periphery of a species range.
1218 Reliance on this assumption can thus confuse interpretation of genetic and demographic
1219 variation in species traits across their range. This illustrates the need for a more systematic
1220 evaluation of variation in both habitat quality and availability across species ranges in which
1221 the spatial (and temporal) structure of the environmental matrix and species metapopulation
1222 dynamics, in terms of dispersal and gene flow (Sork *et al.*, 1999; Holt & Keitt, 2000), are
1223 characterized and treated more fully.

1224 Although few studies have investigated spatial patterns of population occupancy, most have
1225 found decreasing numbers of populations (increasing isolation) towards the periphery of
1226 species' ranges, as predicted by the CPH (Section IV.2a; a in Fig. 8). By contrast, most
1227 empirical studies show that other demographic and morphological traits (e.g. local abundance,
1228 survival, fecundity, size) do not systematically follow either the geographical predictions of
1229 the CPH (Section IV.2a,b.; b and c in Fig 8) or other theoretical models for the formation of
1230 range limits (e.g. Kirkpatrick & Barton, 1997; Keitt *et al.*, 2001). Abundance and population
1231 performance have been found to vary across local ecological gradients, emphasizing again
1232 that ecological and geographical gradients do not always go hand in hand (Section V.2; l and
1233 m in Fig. 8). In addition, different vital rates of a species may respond to different
1234 environmental axes, and their optimal conditions may exhibit different positions along these
1235 axes (m in Fig. 8; Vilellas *et al.*, 2015).

1236 We thus propose that geographical variation in species' occupancy may be the consequence of
1237 the interaction between geographical and ecological gradients in relation to spatially auto-
1238 correlated environmental variables that do not always track geographical gradients. This can
1239 contribute to why species show deviation from the gradual central–peripheral pattern
1240 proposed within the CPH (p in Fig. 8). On the other hand, given that the abundance of

1241 individuals follows local ecological conditions, and that these conditions are not always less
1242 suitable in peripheral sites, we expect abundance to fluctuate across the range in relation to
1243 the occurrence of sites where the ecological requirements of a species are met (q in Fig. 8).
1244 Even though marginal conditions may be more frequent at the periphery, populations could
1245 persist in favourable environments both in the centre and the periphery of the range, which
1246 will translate into lower population occupancy in the periphery but similar abundance of
1247 individuals. We also found that abundance appears to be more geographically structured in
1248 vagile than sessile organisms, possibly due to their dependence on more spatially
1249 autocorrelated environmental variables (Section IV.3; Repasky, 1991; Gilman, 2005; Guo *et*
1250 *al.*, 2005). In vagile species, abundance may follow the distribution pattern of population
1251 occupancy (p in Fig. 8) and the predictions of the CPH. The different vital rates of a species
1252 do not systematically show the same geographical pattern, and could depend on the spatial
1253 configuration of their particular environmental requirements and/or of the other vital rates (r
1254 in Fig. 8). Further investigations on how the different components of species' demographic
1255 performance are related to each other and to different environmental variables at different
1256 geographical scales could contribute to our understanding of species distribution limits
1257 (Schurr *et al.*, 2012; Ehrlén & Morris, 2015). In this context, developing the next generation
1258 of species distribution models represents a particularly promising line of inquiry (Pagel &
1259 Schurr, 2012; Merow *et al.*, 2014).

1260 Our results clearly identify the impact of spatial isolation on geographical patterns of genetic
1261 variation. Peripheral isolates may incur genetic drift and lower gene flow, and consequently
1262 harbour lower genetic diversity and higher differentiation (Section IV.4; d and e in Fig. 8).
1263 However, we did not find a consistent pattern of gradually decreasing genetic diversity and
1264 increasing differentiation within species' geographic ranges, from the centre towards the
1265 periphery (Section IV.2c; d and e in Fig. 8). For many species, genetic diversity might instead

1266 decrease gradually from past refugial areas (characterized by high environmental stability
1267 over glaciation cycles) towards more recently colonized areas through multiple founder events
1268 (Section VI; i and j in Fig. 8). The temporal dynamics of environmental conditions and its
1269 consequences on species' geographic ranges might therefore have a stronger impact on the
1270 broad distribution of genetic variation than current static environmental conditions (n and o in
1271 Fig. 8).

1272 We therefore propose that within-population genetic diversity may in general reach its
1273 optimum in refugial areas (or in admixture zones for species having multiple scattered
1274 refugia), decrease gradually towards more recently founded populations, and finally decrease
1275 abruptly in peripherally isolated populations located at both the rear and leading edges of the
1276 geographic range (s in Fig. 8). For genetic differentiation, the opposite pattern may occur (t in
1277 Fig. 8) but, as recommended previously by Eckert *et al.* (2008), further studies should
1278 investigate its generality using a standardized methodology. Finally, whether spatial patterns
1279 in gene flow and adaptive genetic diversity reflect those of neutral genetic variation remains
1280 relatively poorly known (Reed & Frankham, 2001; Sexton *et al.*, 2011, 2014; Gould *et al.*,
1281 2014). More empirical evidence is necessary to test theoretical models predicting the
1282 geographical distribution of these different facets of genetic variation, the causes of range
1283 limits, and the potential adaptation of peripheral populations to a changing environment
1284 (Sexton *et al.*, 2009; Lavergne *et al.*, 2010; Hoffmann & Sgrò, 2011).

1285 Finally, the long-term dynamics of species ranges does not primarily influence the distribution
1286 of current species' demographic performance (Section VI; f–h in Fig. 8); short-term effects
1287 such as those produced by ongoing global change could potentially reshape such variation
1288 (Channell & Lomolino, 2000; Doak & Morris, 2010). Monitoring changes in demographic
1289 performance of populations located both at the rear and the leading edges of species ranges is
1290 therefore of particular importance for future work (Hampe & Petit, 2005; Purves, 2009).

1291 In retrospect, despite the inaccuracies and imperfections of the CPH, much has been gained in
1292 terms of our understanding of the biogeography of range limits since the appearance of its
1293 first hypotheses and predictions. Although the geographical position of populations within
1294 species ranges may not be a perfect proxy for genetic and demographic performance, the CPH
1295 has stimulated a large number of studies allowing a better understanding of the distribution of
1296 intraspecific variation. Moreover, the production of both empirical and theoretical work
1297 inspired by the CPH will further help to develop novel process-based models (combining
1298 ecological, demographic, and evolutionary information) predicting species distributions in
1299 space and time (Brown *et al.*, 1995; Buckley & Kingsolver, 2012; Fordham *et al.*, 2014;
1300 Ehrlén & Morris, 2015).

1301

1302 **VIII. CONCLUSIONS**

1303 (1) After more than a century of study, thought and discussion, the centre–periphery
1304 hypothesis (CPH) has stimulated an immense interest in the understanding of the complex
1305 factors shaping the distribution of genetic and demographic variation across species ranges.
1306 Our review clearly shows that the CPH is however far from being a general rule common to
1307 all species and their traits.

1308 (2) In addition to the relative position of populations within a geographic range, which alone
1309 cannot explain the distribution of genetic and demographic variation in all species, the relative
1310 effects and possible interactions between geographical, ecological, and historical gradients are
1311 of paramount importance in shaping variation. The interdependence of different traits across
1312 such gradients are of great importance for understanding patterns of variation that are not a
1313 simple translation of cause–effect relationships for individual traits or gradients.

1314 (3) The distribution of genetic diversity may reflect both historical and contemporary factors
1315 associated with post-glacial range dynamics and spatial and ecological isolation. For many

1316 temperate species a latitudinal gradient often confounds central–peripheral and rear–leading
1317 edge effects. Conducting more studies at the rear edge, as well as across the whole ranges of
1318 species within other biogeographic regions (i.e. tropical, Mediterranean, desert, boreal),
1319 would be most helpful here.

1320 (4) Genetic differentiation among populations shows highest values in peripheral isolates and
1321 lowest values in refugial areas. However, this pattern is confounded by methodological issues
1322 and more systematic and standardized studies are needed. In this respect, it is now particularly
1323 important to disentangle the relative effects of geographical and environmental isolation.

1324 (5) Overall, species abundance does not follow the CPH. Ecological conditions do not
1325 systematically follow geographical gradients, which may still have emergent influences on
1326 some factors (population occupancy) but not others (abundance of individuals). Population
1327 occupancy may relate to a lower availability of ecologically suitable sites at the periphery of
1328 the range, whereas abundance within suitable sites may be more related to environmental
1329 quality.

1330 (6) In many species, demographic traits (i.e. population growth rate, survival, growth,
1331 fecundity, recruitment) do not follow the CPH. Local ecological, as well as density-dependent
1332 effects may thus be more influential than the position of the populations within the range
1333 (each rate being impacted differently by these factors, and differently among species).

1334 (7) Finally, setting conservation priorities for populations simply according to their position
1335 within the range does not necessarily provide a representative selection of high-priority sites;
1336 the ecological, demographic, or genetic value of populations for conservation is not strictly
1337 related to geographic position.

1338

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1350

1351 X. REFERENCES

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